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LANGUAGE OF INTERNET FOLKLORE: SOCIO-TECHNOLOGICAL ENVIRONMENT AND VIRTUAL COMMUNICATION

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ЯЗЫК ИНТЕРНЕТ-ФОЛЬКЛОРА: СОЦИАЛЬНО-ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ СРЕДА И ВИРТУАЛЬНАЯ КОМУНИКАЦИЯ

Abstract.

The emergence and development of information and communication technologies influenced the appearing of epochal processes, the emergence of changes not only in the means and methods of communication, but also in the essence and content of social communication. The discovery of writing after oral speech is characterized by new possibilities in the understanding and expression of reality. However, electronic, digital and virtual means of communication have led to the emergence of social communication and relations on completely different channels and platforms, as a result of which the essence of the socio-cultural environment has changed. In the article in the context of the epochal processes the cultural dynamics of folklore is investigated, the typological differences of oral, written and virtual communication images are determined, finally, the language of Internet folklore is involved in the analysis. It is determined that although communication in virtual social networks is carried out through writing, the prototype of this language is the emotion of orality. In this regard, the language of social networks is determined not by the spelling rules of the Azerbaijani literary language, but by the principles of orthoepy. As a result of the study, it is found that the anonymity and privacy of the Internet allows to eliminate psychological barriers, freedom, indifference to rules and norms, which determines the sociopsychological situation of the environment as a whole. This reality has an impact primarily on the language in which the nature of the virtual social environment is reflected.

Аннотация.

Появление и развитие информационно-коммуникационных технологий повлияло на возникновение эпохальных процессов, на изменение не только средств и способов общения, но и сущности и содержания социальной коммуникации. Открытие письма после устной речи характеризуется новыми возможностями в восприятии и выражении действительности. Электронные, цифровые и виртуальные средства коммуникации привели к тому, что социальное общение и отношения стали осуществляться на совершенно разных каналах и платформах, что в конечном итоге изменило характер социокультурной среды. В контексте указанных эпохальных процессов в статье прослеживается культурная динамика фольклора, выявляются типологические различия между устными, письменными и виртуальными формами общения, наконец, в анализ включается язык интернет-фольклора. В статье установлено, что хотя общение в виртуальных социальных сетях осуществляется посредством письма, прототип этого языка основан на эмоциях устной речи. В связи с этим язык социальных сетей определяется не правилами орфографии азербайджанского литературного языка, а принципами орфоэпии. Исследование показало, что способность Интернета обеспечивать анонимность и конфиденциальность приводит к устранению психологических барьеров, свободе и безразличию к правилам и нормам, что в свою очередь определяет социально-психологическое состояние этой среды. Эта реальность также оказывает влияние на язык, который в первую очередь отражает природу виртуальной социальной среды.

Keywords: Internet folklore, virtual communication, socio-technological environment, orality, language

Ключевые слова: интернет-фольклор, виртуальная коммуникация, социально-технологическая среда, устное творчество, язык.

Problem setting: language, writing and culture in the context of epochal changes

It won't be mistake, if one says that one of the conditions of certainty of the cultural typology of each period or level is conditioned by the means and possibilities of communication. Thus, if, on the one hand, the language acts as the creator of the collective social en-

vironment, on the other hand, it serves to organize society, culture, ideology in a single system. Of course, at the initial stage the facts attracting attention such as technological innovation and change begin to shift over time from formal changes to changes in content and meaning. In classical terms, the quantitative change is transformed into qualitative. It means, the technological progress, which arises from the necessary needs

such as obtaining information, communicating, establishing contacts, gaining mobility, improving the tools and processes of labor, is moving towards changing everything that concerns a person, and, ultimately, even the person himself. No matter how long the transition from homo sapiens to info sapiens may take, this is a reality. Today, the technological process surrounds the socio-cultural sphere as a whole, including human and everything connected with him/her. Thus, the technological innovation and transformations have evolved from human “*homo sapiens*” to “*info sapiens*” and “*techno sapiens*” (Kizildagh 2021: 176; Floridi 2014: 84), from “*human*” to “*post human*” (Floridi 2014: 81-95), from “*infor*g” (Gulum 2018: 43; Somerville 2006: 128) into “*cyborg*” (Floridi 2014: 81-95), which led to the transformation, the change in the content and essence of creativity in the context of cultural and communicative dynamics. The content and essence part of this process, are just related to culture, language, folklore and so on.

Technological progress creates changes in all spheres. Sometimes these changes give impetus to epochal processes. It was information revolutions that led to epochal changes in the development of mankind. In particular, the acquisition, memorization, processing and transmission of information were different due to the possibilities of information and communication technologies. For example, with the discovery of writing “... as a carrier of information, it is not only the memory of people, but also the use of material carriers – stone, animal skin, wood and other things began to be used. This important event happened in the history of mankind created opportunities for registration, long-term memorization and dissemination of information in space and time, compared to the previous revolution” (Aliguliyev, Valehov, Mahmudov 2008: 9). Thus, the discovery of writing created the conditions for the followings:

- The possibility of memorizing information, turning it into history and heritage appeared;
- The restriction on the transmission of information in terms of distance has been eliminated;
- There was an opportunity for the reproduction (to increase information), to copy and further expansion of information;
- Finally, writing created a written style, a written culture.

At the next stage after the discovery of writing, the emergence of book printing influenced the wider dissemination of acquired information and knowledge and its preservation for a longer period of time. Naturally, this process played a serious role in the development of mankind, in reaching the broad masses of ideas and philosophical thoughts. No doubt, all of these, in turn, resulted in the preservation of folklore, collective cultural memory, the strengthening of heritage - heir ties/relations.

The discovery of electricity after book printing is characterized by the emergence of the so-called “electronic epoch”. Walter J.Ong, the author of the concept of technologizing of the word naming this level “the second epoch of oral culture” writes that “*The installa-*

tions such as telephone, radio and television, etc. created the epoch of the “second oral culture” (Ong 2005: 133).

After the invention of writing, printing and electricity, one of the most important revolutions in the life of humanity was the discovery of the Internet. The Internet has given impetus to processes that cannot be compared with any of the pre-revolutionary changes:

- It created the possibility of individual communication;
- The borders among peoples and cultures disappeared;
- The virtual twin of real social reality appeared;
- The new social environment was formed for the activity of language, literature, culture, folklore and so on;
- The concepts such as digital technological platform, virtual communication, electronic culture and others were formed.

After the emergence of the Internet, the appearing of technology that includes Web 2.0 – the second generation of Internet services - transformed it from the information and knowledge archive function into the knowledge processing platform. The main innovation here is the activation of people in the process of information discussion and exchange at the expense of participating social networks, the formation of the common information environment. Such situation has transformed the social media into the socio-cultural environment. The social networks such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube are precisely participatory social networks. In fact, this environment introduces all the opportunities needed for digital folklore performance. These opportunities created conditions for the formation of the virtual social environment of the Azerbaijani language and the emergence of folklore resources within this language segment. Thus, the culture that emerged in the verbal communicative environment, later transformed into writing, living in the era of “second orality” on the basis of the abundance of audio information within the electronic epoch, was transformed into a virtual platform with the discovery of the Internet. There is no doubt that each method and channel of communication conditioned the emergence of a self-centered type of culture. Each type of culture reflects the peculiarities of the “language” in which it is expressed.

The influence of technological transformations on the language: socio-psychological factors

The emergence of the interactive social media platform due to the technology of Web 2.0 has transformed the Internet user from a passive listener to an active participant.

American folklorist S.J.Bronner basing on the conception “prosumer” (*formed from the combination of the words “producer” and “consumer”*) by A.Toffler (Toffler 1980: 267) referred the following question: “If the producer and the consumer come together in a shared interactive environment and emerge in the form of a “*producer-consumer*”, “*what will happen?*”” (Bronner 2009: 24). Thus, the presence of each user in virtual social networks in the status of both a receiver

and a producer of the information, and, in terms of folklore studies, the active participation of the Internet user as both a narrator and a listener, distinguished the virtual social environment from the traditional, face-to-face communication environment. Of course, in the creation of information, knowledge, words, not only those who say, but also those who listen, transmit, receive have already become active.

As technological processes deepen, the formal changes are transformed into the content changes;

The virtual social environment is formed on the basis of new social conditions and requirements;

The virtual person/personality gains the experience of living in the virtual environment and the virtual traditions appear;

In the virtual social environment a new behavior, a new tradition, a new reality is created and these are transformed into the language;

In general, the technological innovations and processes affecting the social environment initially have formed a socio-technological platform, as a continuation of it the content and essence of creativity in the context of socio-cultural dynamics have changed. As all these factors are expressed through the language, or rather, they occur on the basis of communication the necessity and possibility of communication emerges, which is incompatible with the “language” of the traditional social environment and is based not only on “talking” and “conversing”, but also on “showing” and “demonstrating” (Garayev 2020). However, it is conditioned by different types of linguistic signs such as virtual communication // electronic communication // hybrid communication and so on.

Folkloric language and metaphorical-symbolic meaning

As it is mentioned above, the language is a system of symbols and signs at the same time. A person’s estimation of himself/herself and reality takes place within the framework of metaphorical-symbolic meanings. Culture, as well as folklore, personifies social reality by metaphorizing it, turning it into symbols and signs. Paying attention to it, we can note that:

- Folklore as a metaphorical-symbolic system is embodied in the process of folkloric communication and in the model of collective thinking;

- The virtual folkloric facts are created, perceived and transmitted precisely within the framework of the metaphorical-symbolic meanings of the language;

- In Internet folklore the folkloric fact with the user appears in a single semiotic process composition: SIGN – POINTER – MARKED

The Internet memes are cultural units that are transmitted from a user to a user through the method of “copy” and imitation, embodying the certain idea or behavior. The literal meaning of this concept, first used by Richard Dawkins (Dawkins 1989), comes from the Greek word “mimeme”, which means “something that is imitated”. “... *It is an idea, a style of behavior that spreads from people to people in the Internet environment, social networks*” (Jafarov 2017: 98).

The Internet “memes” are also metalanguage facts as examples of folkloric creativity. In “memes” the

meaning is created using the universal capabilities of the language – symbolism. Let’s look through a few examples:

URL – 1

In the photo, which combines the image of three different items, the first two items are real traps and the third item – a ring, meaning getting engaged, getting married, is a “trap” in a figurative sense. The folkloric meaning here is expressed in symbolic language - metalanguage.

In other folkloric facts the metaphorical-symbolic meaning is expressed both in signs and words:

URL – 2

URL – 3

The language of the social media and socio-psychological environment: anonymity, freedom and “multilingualism”

The social networks and social media as a whole have an important influence in making the Internet a leading means of communication. In fact, the changes taking place in the Azerbaijani language in the current period are manifested in the virtual social environment, which has emerged as a continuation of the real social environment. However, the communication that occurs in a face-to-face virtual communicative environment corresponds to socio-technological conditions. Therefore, one of the factors determining the language of social media is the requirements arising from the digital-technological structure. As an example, we can show some of the following limitations:

However, Facebook is suitable for all types of information, while Twitter is dominated by the written text, YouTube is mainly video, Instagram is dominated by photo and video resources;

Text shares on Twitter are limited to 140 characters. But this fact makes it necessary to maximally concreteness for the expression of thought (slogan-text);

The short, video-format information in “TikTok” creates, along with attractiveness, attention span and abundance of information without content.

One of the most basic opportunities that social media, virtual social networks create for users is anonymity. Each user can sign up for social networks using a nickname or a fake name. However, it creates conditions for the anonymity of the users. But the social media anonymity has a different socio-psychological nature:

- a) It provides privacy;
- b) It creates freedom in relation to norms and rules;
- c) It removes the psychological barriers;
- d) It forms a virtual personality different from the real;

The situation caused by the anonymity nature of social media in the behavior of a virtual individual or social group has a number of effects on cultural creativity:

- anti-norm;
- anti-stereotype;
- anti-tradition;
- individuality;
- informality, etc.

The environment that forms on social media is characterized as a multivoicedness environment (Erdoghd, Yumruksuz 2021: 174). It is a carnivalistic effect created by an environment consisting of a multitude of individuals, conditioned by the digital-technological structure, communicative nature and dynamic content of social media. However, this environment has a dialogical, parodic and ironic character. It eliminates the authoritarian structure with its anti-hierarchical nature. Thus, depending on the digital-technological basis of social networks, the hierarchical structure of social relations here, as well as the meaning and content arising from their reproduction – vernacular specificity – the language of social media is determined. Of course, this language is free in relation to the official rules and laws, norms and principles of the Azerbaijani literary language. It means, the language in social networks manifests itself as a spelling error, a dictation mistake, violation of phonetic, lexical, grammatical norms from the point of view of the norms and principles of the literary language.

Socio-technological reality: digital platform and literary language

Of course, although the technological progress creates quite wide opportunities for obtaining, storing and processing information, it also has some negative aspects. In general, the technological progress has both positive and negative aspects:

Positive aspects:

- To obtain, memorize, transmit, modify information in a convenient way, etc.;
- To ensure the need for communication and socialization;
- The possibility of fast communication, etc.;

Negative aspects:

- The extreme abundance of information;
- The problem of concentration;
- The inclination from the creative thinking to mechanical, technical skills, ready-made resources;

- Non-compliance with language rules, etc.;
- Rapid popularization of spelling mistakes;

Language of the internet: oral, written or hybrid

The linguistic typology of the Internet is formed by the facts of communication in social media and networks. There are some points that attract attention here:

- To use the words belonging to the foreign languages;
- To write as it is pronounced or said;
- To use the dialect facts and local words;
- To use different abbreviations and shorts such as OMG; LOL, etc.;
- To use of emoji: ☺ ☹
- To accept the new words into the language: “fake”, “chat”, “troll”, “hashtag”;
- Making spelling mistakes: “ə-e”, “ö-o”, “ü-u”, “ş-sh”, “ğ-g”;
- Incorrect use of punctuation marks or their absence.

In all cases, the virtual communication takes place on the basis of the alphabet of any language. The virtual communication is established by letters on the keyboard. But the usage of some points such as the flexibility of communication, writing as it is spoken, the character of emotionally “talking”, “chatting”, not using the punctuation marks correctly, the use of emoticons makes this communication verbal. Thus, although the virtual communication is formally written (in letters, with signs), in its psychological prototype one can see the emotion of orality.

The verbliness of the Internet language shows itself in a number of signs:

- The working language of the social networks - Internet corresponds to the daily life style;
- Flexible communication makes comfortable communication – an informal format that does not follow the rules of the language necessary;
- The expectation of language rules, spelling principles, stylistic norms in the virtual communication is not emotionally “accepted”, because it creates “coldness”, “formality”;
- In contrast, the use of dialect facts creates an “intimate environment”;
- Informal communication and daily life style make swearing and unethical expression relevant.

Thus, violation of the rules of the literary language in the virtual social environment is associated not only with literacy or illiteracy, but also with socio-psychological factors belonging to its genesis.

Conclusion

Digital-technological transformations, as in all spheres, are manifested in the sociocultural environment, in cultural creativity, which is its manifestation, as well as in linguistic facts. At the current period the facts of linguistic creativity appearing in the virtual social networks of Azerbaijani language are incompatible with the laws and rules, norms and principles of the Azerbaijani literary language. Of course, it has its own reasons.

Although the communication on the Internet is carried out through writing, the prototype of this lan-

guage is the emotion of orality. In this regard, the language of social networks is determined not by the spelling rules of the Azerbaijani literary language, but by the principles of orthoepy. However, there are exceptions to this principle as well. Thus, sometimes the principles of orthoepy of the literary language are replaced by the tradition of dialect, local pronunciation. As the Internet is open to the users from any social group (literate, illiterate, etc.), the state of the language in social networks also manifests itself accordingly. In other words, the level of reading and writing skills of the users in accordance with the rules of the literary language is directly proportional to the state of the language in social networks. However, we believe that the reason for non-compliance with the rules of the language in virtual social networks is not only due to the level of acquisition of reading and writing skills, this process is due to the sociopsychological situation inherent in the Internet environment.

The possibility of anonymity and privacy of the Internet gives rise to the elimination of psychological barriers, freedom, indifference to rules and norms, which determines the sociopsychological situation of this environment as a whole (Quliyev 2022: 113). This reality has an impact primarily on the language in which the nature of the virtual social environment is reflected. At the same time, the breadth of the possibilities of influence of social networks contributes to the rapid popularization and misappropriation of facts that are violations of the norm and spelling errors in terms of the literary language.

Moreover, since communication on social media has emerged on the digital-technological platform, the language here has to adapt to a number of restrictions and requirements. This process is subject to formal changes in the initial case (shortening of the text, concreting, using signs, etc.), then by influencing the stylistic specificity, it also manifests itself in the content-essence plan.

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